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Review Article

IMPOTENT MEN AND INFERTILE WOMEN-REVIEW STUDY.¹Dr Kalsoom Arshad,²Dr Maryam,³Dr Tehreem Fatima.^{1,2,3}MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Infertility occurs when partners cannot conceive after unprotected sex. It may occur if one of the partners is not able to originate or the woman cannot carry the pregnancy to the full extent. The definition of infertility is usually written as not being able to conceive after a year of sexual intercourse with your partner without the use of contraception. Blocked fallopian tubes, ovulation problems, and endometriosis are some reasons that cause infertility in women. Male infertility includes the problems of quality and quantity of sperms. Other genetic problems are there too. Some environmental, psychological, health and dietary problems can have a huge hand in infertility too. Men and women can reduce infertility by managing their lifestyles. Female infertility problems can be treated significantly by various treatments.

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INTRODUCTION:

Infertility occurs when partners cannot conceive after unprotected sex. It may occur if one of the partners is not able to originate or the woman cannot carry the pregnancy to the full extent. The definition of infertility is usually written as not being able to conceive after a year of sexual intercourse with your partner without the use of contraception. [1] In the USA, there is around 10 percent of girls, from age 15 to 43 face difficulty in conceiving, or remaining pregnant. Moreover, about 65-80 million couples around the world face this problem of infertility. [2] Somewhere around 45 to 50 percent of the cases are seen to come from the factor influenced by men. The estimation shows a rate of 11.25% to 15.5% in Canada, that is, out of every seven couples, one of them faces infertility. [3]

Infertility has been growing ever since 1990, the amount has increased from 42 million to 48 million till 2010. [4] among those 12 percent of couples facing infertility problems around the world, half of the cases are due to infertile men. There are 36 to 40 % of cases where men are infertile and, 20 to 32% cases where women are infertile, which is related to a couple of other factors as well. [5] Infertility may also occur due to consecutive abortions and deliveries with multiple hereditary diseases. [6]

MATERIAL AND AIMS:

This study aims to find out the cause behind infertility and the risk factors. It discusses the primary and secondary causes of infertility. The results are shared in detail in the following:

RESULTS:

The major factors that are seen to be the cause of infertility were disordered reproductive system, diseases of the reproductive system, smoking, drugs, immunity, cell phone use and other sexual ferocity, psychosocial stress, obesity, diet, and chronic disease. These are some known factors that reduce the chances of a successful pregnancy.

Reproductive system disorders:**Some common issues in women:**

Some article says that female infertility can give some hint about the ovulation issues, structural problems for example damage in fallopian tube or endometriosis.

Endometriosis: is a benign estrogen-dependent inflammatory disease that occurs due to ectopic endometrial implants. It is seen that this disease affects about 1-13% of adult women, who can carry the pregnancy.

The congenital disorders, inside the womb, muscles and tissue glands, sex glands, and adhesion are also the factors reducing fertility. [7]

Some common issues in men:

The prostate gland, other sex organs, and seminal vesicle release a fluid called semen. Semen is a milky fluid released from the penis of a man during sex. It consists of fluid and sperms.

The sperms present in the fluid are produced in the testicles. At the point when a man discharges and delivers semen through his penis, the fundamental liquid, called semen, helps to transport its sperms toward the eggs. The following issues can occur:

Lesser sperm count: when a man discharges less number of sperms. The man releasing sperm less than 15 million is views as a low count. About 32 percent of couples face this problem of lesser sperm count and thus they cannot conceive.

Low mobility of sperms: the sperm can't swim and do not reach each egg which it should be reaching.

Genital infection diseases:

The untreated sexually transmitted infections are also one of the factors damaging men's and women's reproductive systems. Chlamydia and gonorrhea are the most popular STIs that leads toward reducing fertility. However, the scary thing is that it has no symptoms; therefore, it cannot be predicted and treated. The women can get pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) if the chlamydia is left untreated. PID is a very risky problem that causes inflammation in the upper body part of the reproductive system and the related organs in women. [8] Women can also develop the risk for ectopic pregnancy, infertility in the fallopian tube, and chronic pelvic disorder if they have PID. [9] In the 14550 reasons behind the treatment of IVF, fallopian tube problems are the most important ones. [10]

The age factor:

The infertility risks increase with age. Young people suffering from infertility can still have more hope for fertility and improvement by maintenance and pregnancy health. Women before their 30s and men before their 35s are more capable to have fertility and healthy pregnancy. Therefore, the couple should know each other's age for better outcomes.

The hormonal disorders:

Hormonal factors also play an important role in infertility. Some commonly known factors are hypothyroidism, hyperprolactinemia (also known as

higher hormonal level in a male), and luteal phase problems (known as low level of progesterone). This can be a serious issue for women leading to infertility. The inability of women to carry pregnancy may due to irregular hormone levels cause too high or too low hormonal production in them. The symptoms are irregular monthly menstrual issues, excessive gain or loss of weight, lower abdominal cramps, and very little or excessive bleeding, etc. This hormonal disturbance can seriously affect the functioning of glands and thus leading to some serious problems. Birth controlling pills, hypertension, and hyperthyroidism like problems affect the working of the gland. If any gland encounters any trouble, the mess can stop the process of ovulation, and hence complications happen in pregnancy.

Smoking and alcohol impact on pregnancy:

The consumption of chemicals such as nicotine, cyanide, and CO in cigarettes destroys ovules. Unfortunately, the replacement of ovules is impractical until today. This shows that a female smoker reaches menopause about 4 years earlier. Female smokers and non-smokers do not get pregnant at the same rate. 30%-reduced chances of pregnancy are present in smoking women through IVF than in non-smoking women.

It is seen that 41% of the infertile men are due to smoking. In men, the quality and the quantity of sperms reduces to dangerous levels due to smoking and thus increasing infertility. Abnormal sperms are formed and are unable to fertilize an egg. [11] infertility in non-smokers men and women is almost half than the smoker men and women.

The impact of immune responses:

Immunity plays an important role in healthy sex. For example in RM-Recurrent Miscarriages, implantation failure, and infertility. It represents that the success of pregnancy depends on the maternal immunity response toward increasing semi-allogeneic fetus. Systemic immunity is responsible for the embryo implantation process. These processes play a critical part in the contribution to pregnancy. In female sexual functions, the natural killer cells play a significant role. The cells relate to inductive failures. [12]

The impact of mobile use:

The radio waves emitted by mobile phones and laptops reduce the quality of sperms and cause disturbed functioning of the body. Male sexual abilities are affected by many real mechanisms. For example, the thermal effect and non-thermal effect

rely upon the impact of cellphones on biological systems. The testicles absorb radiation more than other organs because it is a shallow organ. Oxidative stress is the major cause of infertility in men. Free radical sperms are also caused by mobile phones.

Effect of Sexual violence:

Literature and many studies have shown that sexual violence leads to infertility. Being sexually dysfunctional and infertile is more common in women who have faced sexual harassment more than thrice. This is due to mental trauma. A much-known relation between infertility and sexual violence can be explained by the fallopian tube infertility. However, the reasons other than this failure are harder to examine. The test for such reasons are un-reliable, therefore, there are an unknown amount of reasons for non-tubal infertility due to undetectable tubal infertility. [13]

Effect of Anxiety:

Although infertility can cause anxiety in the life of a man, the direct relation of this anxiety with men's infertility is not clear. Due to the problems of infertility for whatever reasons, men can have severe stress and anxiety in their life, which will decrease the chance to have healthy sexual intercourse among the partners [14]

Effect of Obesity:

Studies have declared that obese women or having abdominal fat can cause severe infertility problems in them. Also, these infertility problems are harder to treat. Women with having Body Mass Index higher than 25 have a lower rate of pregnancy than those with a BMI lesser than 25. Obesity relates to PSOC (polycystic ovary syndrome) that causes infertility in women 22. An article shows that about 10.2 % of the infertile or sub-fertile women are diagnosed with DOR (Diminished Reduced Ovarian). [15] During the childbearing age, PCOS is a major reason behind infertility. [16] 30-69% obese women diagnosed with PCOS.

Effect of Diseases:

Fertility in men and women is affected by multiple automatic systems named Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). Due to the disease activity in women and men, the genital tract may be affected due to cytotoxic treatment. Some diseases stop successful fertility, reduces the implantation in the uterine and carrying pregnancy, and cause infertility. [17] Varicocele is a pathological enlargement of the pampiniform venous plexus in the scrotum that affects testicular function and can lead to infertility.

Unknown factors:

Several unknown reasons cause infertility. Further research is needed to claim the problems, which are still unknown to us. There are certain special factors in men and women that are still unknown.

DISCUSSION:

WHO reports so many environmental and sexual interaction factors that affect fertility. [18] Some factors are in the control of the individual such as nutrition, obesity control, stress management, smoking, and drugs. However, there are still some unknown and unclear factors that cause infertility, and needs more research to be done. This research article tries to explain every single aspect that affects infertility and the reason behind it.

RESULTS:

Blocked fallopian tubes, ovulation problems, and endometriosis are some reasons that cause infertility in women. Male infertility includes the problems of quality and quantity of sperms. Other genetic problems are there too. Some environmental, psychological, health and dietary problems can have a huge hand in infertility too. Men and women can reduce infertility by managing their lifestyles. Female infertility problems can be treated significantly by various treatments.

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